

Method Guide

JUSTNature | Work Package 7, Task 7.2

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HOW TO USE THIS GUIDE

To enhance collaborative governance and the planning of Nature-based Solution (NbS) interventions in one's city, one needs to get to know and delve into certain features, processes, and ongoing dynamics of governance and planning. For this purpose, it can be useful to speak with local stakeholders to gather various points of view in a structured and comprehensive manner. To gather this information, it is possible to conduct interviews, surveys, or collective interviews (called focus groups) with citizens, technicians, municipal administrators, and other stakeholders in the urban context. This guide offers support in doing so.

It is not necessary for you to read the entire document. Select one or more parts of the report according to your needs:

- Section 1 helps you choose the most suitable method for data collection—interviews, surveys, or focus groups—and formulate effective questions (Section 1.2).
- In Section 2, read table 2 for a quick comparison of the methods, then go directly to the section that concerns the method you are interested in, for more detail.
- Once you have read the main characteristics of the selected method, the checklists in Section 3 provide tips on what you need to do before, during and after a survey (3.1), interview (3.2), or focus group (3.3).
- In Annex 2 you will find examples of questions formulated for selected indicators and methods. If you need help formulating questions for another indicator or method, please reach out to us!

1 INTRODUCTION

As part of the JUSTNature project, each city has chosen relevant objectives for the co-governance of nature-based solutions (NbS) and related indicators to assess progress towards them. This document serves as a comprehensive guide to data collection methods related to these indicators. We focus on three common data collection methods: **surveys, interviews, and focus groups** and look at selecting the right one for your purpose, pros and cons, and key distinctions between them (Part 2), as well as a checklist for what to keep in mind before, during and after you carry out each one. An appendix includes factsheets for selected indicators, including tips and sample questions. Further questions and tips can be developed on-demand – please get in touch if you have specific needs.

This guide is part of a broader set of supporting materials. Find an overview under the 'Resources' tab [here](#).

In addition, independent of the method you apply, it is important to clarify the objectives of the project and the applied method focus group and to explain to participants how their personal data and contributions will be handled. You can use and adapt the [information sheet and consent form template](#) developed by Eurac.

1.1 Selecting a method

While no method is perfect and “provides 100% accurate and reliable information” (Kumar 2011, p. 139), selecting the right method for what you want to measure is an important starting point. Selecting and defining an indicator goes hand in hand with selecting a method. In other words, the method and indicator are interdependent. This means that when indicators are adjusted for the local context, often the method also need to be adjusted.

Later in this guide, we have suggested methods which might suit your indicators. However, since both indicators and methods almost always need to be further specified to meet your local needs, it's worth reflecting on key points to consider before selecting a method:

1. case or scale
 - Think about the context in which the indicator will be applied. Examples are: pilot project, the city district in which the pilot intervention is to be developed, the city, or organization such as a specific department, or the whole municipal organization.
2. potential target groups/respondents
 - Think about who can provide the information you are looking for. A stakeholder analyse can help to identify potential target groups/respondents.
3. data to be collected
 - Think about what you would like to know or how you want to use the data. The purpose of the data can be often linked to the indicator.
4. whether the method is suitable for the subject matter
 - For example, focus groups are not suitable for confidential topics.
5. the respondent group size

- For example, surveys are more suitable to retrieve data from large population groups, such as citizens of a neighbourhood.
6. the respondent group's character
 - For example, focus groups are not suitable for groups with big power disparities.
 7. the depth of information you need to get useful insights
 - For example, focus groups and interviews can provide more in-depth data than a survey.
 8. data processing skills and resources
 - For example, interviews and focus groups often require transcription and their analysis is labour intensive, while surveys might require some level of statistical skills.

1.2 Asking questions

Just like indicators and methods, questions also usually need to be adapted to the local context and needs, as well as to the method applied. The way you ask a question in a group discussion is different to in a written survey. Here we provide some guidelines on different kinds of questions, which ones are most suitable for which methods, and how to formulate good questions.

Open-ended and closed questions

For closed questions, possible responses are already provided, and the respondent only needs to tick the box for the most suitable answer. Closed questions can be answered in different ways: with a simple “yes or no”, with a range of options on a spectrum (Likert-scale), lists of possible response(s), or through ranking. If working with closed questions with listed responses, Kumar (2011) recommends adding the option “other, please describe” to accommodate any non-foreseen responses. Unlike closed questions, open-ended questions do not provide any pre-formulated responses from which the respondent can choose, but the respondent needs to formulate his/her own response.

Table 1. Examples of open-ended and closed questions.

Open questions	Closed questions
Please give a short description of the activities that you have undertaken for this governance action in the last 6 months	Is the indicator selection still relevant for the monitoring of progress made on the formulated objectives or outcomes? <i>Please rate your personal view between 1 (not at all) and 5 (to a great extent)</i> 1 2 3 4 5 <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
Which difficulties did the governance action encounter over the last 6 months?	Which external actor groups been involved in the design of the NbS intervention? <input type="checkbox"/> citizens <input type="checkbox"/> nature conservation organisations <input type="checkbox"/> water shed management <input type="checkbox"/> public schools <input type="checkbox"/> researchers <input type="checkbox"/> other, please specify

Open-ended questions provide in general **qualitative data** in the form of written or spoken text or images, although also numerical data can be asked for. Open-ended questions allow respondents to answer more freely (Kumar, 2011), which results in often deeper and more varied responses. This freedom, however, can also be problematic, when responses do not fit the question (Kumar, 2011), which can happen particularly when the question is ambiguous. Rich and varied responses without clearly predefined categories can provide a lot of insight and allow unexpected themes to emerge but can also make it more complicated to interpret the meaning. There is also higher chance for the interviewer's bias to influence the results as he/she will interpret the responses from his/her point of view.

Closed questions can provide qualitative data, but more often will provide **quantitative** or numerical data through pre-defined categories. As responses are already categorised, it's easier to summarise them and compare across all respondents. However, responses to closed questions often lack depth and variety in comparison with open-ended questions. The provided response categories might also be biased by the interviewer's own experiences, interests and blind spots. Even when the option "other" is provided, respondents are more likely to select the most agreeable answer from the provided responses, which might not reflect the respondent's ideas (Kumar, 2011).

Table 2. Overview of different closed questions (adapted from SurveyMonkey, 2024)

Type of closed question	Description, pros and cons
Multiple choice	Respondents can select one or more predetermined answers. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to answer, easy to analyse • Requires clear distinctive answers • Limited choice can cause bias • Add "other" as last answer
Ordinal scale	Respondents select the number on the scale that best fits their response <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Values of the scale need to be explained
Likert scale	Respondents provide a response on a scale of 3, 5 or 7 in how far they "agree or disagree" with the question <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good for feedback • Measuring opinions or attitudes
Ranking	Respondents rank answers by preference <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows understanding of preferences in comparison to each other • Take more time to answer • Requires familiarity with each answer
Image choice	Respondents can select images as answers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To evaluate visual qualities
Mapping	Respondents can indicate points or even areas on a map <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows to gain spatial data • Especially with indication of areas, the data analysis can be resource-intensive
Slider	Respondents can evaluate something on a numerical scale <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive • Quantifies sentiment on an individual and aggregate level

Tips for formulating questions

To formulate effective questions for any method, Kumar (2011) provides the following guidelines:

- Use simple and everyday language and avoid jargon without explanation (e.g., NbS, governance)
- Do not ask ambiguous questions that can be interpreted in different ways
- Ask simple questions and avoid asking questions within questions
- Address only one issue per question
 - Do not ask leading questions (i.e. a question that already has part of the answer implied) (e.g., “it is difficult to include citizens in your project, right?”)
- Do not ask questions based on presumptions. First try to clarify presumptions with neutral questions.
 - e.g., instead of asking “Why do you not collaborate with the department of infrastructure?”, first ask “with which departments do you currently not collaborate?” and then ask, “could you explain why you are currently not collaborating with the department of infrastructure?”.

Not only do the individual questions need careful formulation, but also the sequence of questions needs to be considered. Respondents expect that questions logically build up on another. Questions are often answered with still the previous questions and answers in mind. Sudden changes of topics can confuse respondents, which can result in answers that do not match the question.

Before carrying out your survey, interview or focus group, we recommend testing the questions with a smaller audience that is similar to the target audience. The test group can check the questions according to the above-mentioned tips for formulating questions.

2 A CLOSER LOOK AT SURVEYS, INTERVIEWS AND FOCUS GROUPS

The table below provides an overview of the three methods with options, advantages and disadvantages of each.

Table 2. Overview of the data collection methods surveys, interviews and focus groups (Adapted from Creswell (2014) and Kumar (2011)).

Method	Options	Advantages	Disadvantages
Survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire in person, per email, per post, or online • Individual or in groups • Qualitative and quantitative • Open and closed questions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large groups can be reached • Allows to reach respondents in different locations • Less expensive in terms of time, human and financial resources • Offers greater anonymity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires careful consideration of questions and format • Response rate is often low • Responses might not be representative, as only specific groups reply • At times statistical data analysis skills required
Interview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In person interview, one-on-one, face-to-face or through videoconferencing applications or through telephone • Structured or semi-structured • Mainly open questions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful for phenomena that are difficult to observe (e.g., ideas, perceptions, relations, processes) • Allows for rich in-depth data • Information about phenomena in the past can be provided • The interviewer has control over the line of questioning • Questions can be clarified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The information can be coloured through the views and biases of interviewees • The interviewer's presence can influence responses • Not everybody can express him/herself well verbally • The data analysis can be time consuming
Focus group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group interview, face-to-face or through videoconferencing applications • Workshop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows exchange, discussion and learning between participants • Allows for idea development • Different workshop techniques can be used to gather or select ideas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Much dependent on group and power dynamics • Not all topics are easily discussed in groups (e.g., personal, political) • Requires moderation skills

2.1 Surveys

A survey (or questionnaire) is essentially a written list of questions that is read, interpreted, and answered independently by the respondent him- or herself (Kumar, 2011). Surveys can be conducted in different ways, e.g., digitally or on paper, remotely or in person, alone or in a group setting (Kumar, 2011).

In-person or remote?

Respondents often fill in a questionnaire at work or at home, but they can also be administered **in person**. This has as benefit that any questions regarding the survey can be answered on the spot. Moreover, you can reach out to people in public or semi-public spaces and in this way steer the selection of respondents. For example, you can set a target to have an equal number of responses from both women and men. In-person surveys allow also to better target specific groups by conducting the surveys in **locations** which they frequent. For example, in the proximity of universities, it is more likely you will be able to reach students. Besides location, also the factor of **time** needs to be considered. Preferably, respondents are asked when they have time. Train and bus stations are for this reason a popular spot for surveys as people might be more open to participating while waiting for their connection. In-person surveys can also be conducted **at people's homes** or by **telephone**.

The difficulty with individual in-person surveys is that they are time consuming, and therefore less cost-efficient in terms of human resources. A frequent solution is to work with volunteers or students. Another option is to conduct surveys in **group** settings, e.g., participants can be asked to fill in a questionnaire after a workshop or meeting. Group settings offer the opportunity to answer any questions that arise about the survey, and increased response rates due to direct contact and 'peer pressure'.

Paper or digital?

The benefit of digital questionnaires is that they are **accessible, cost-efficient, and easy to distribute to large groups of people**. Everybody with internet access can partake. However, for people with no access to internet or digital skills, potentially elderly people or young children, a **printed questionnaires** might be a better solution. Printed questionnaires can also be sent by mail to groups for which addresses are known and, in this way, a larger audience can be reached. E.g., all inhabitants of a specific street or neighbourhood. The disadvantage of mailed questionnaires is the extra step respondents need to take to send in their responses, which can lower response rates. Paper formats also have the disadvantage that all the data still needs to be digitalised for analysis. For individual in-person surveys, we can therefore see increasingly the use of tablets or smartphones.

For **digital questionnaires**, there are nowadays many different **providers** available, e.g., Google Forms, Survey Monkey, Empirio and Lime Survey. The options within the different providers can differ, depending on whether the free or paid version is used. It is recommendable to check the different options providers offer and to see which one fits best to the questions, their format, and targeted respondents. Also, check their data protection rules, and whether these comply with your data storage rules. Data protection concerns can be a reason for respondents not to partake in surveys on some platforms, such as Google Forms.

Question types and structure

Surveys can contain **open** and **closed** questions or a combination of both. As questions are being interpreted by the respondents, often without the possibility for them to clarify what's meant, questions need to be **concise, clear and easy to understand**. If questions are unclear, it is likely that answers won't be accurate. As a set, the questions need to be **clearly organised**, and logically following up on one another to create the sense of a conversation, e.g., through supporting explanations and **alternating question types** (closed question, followed by open-ended question to allow respondents to elaborate on the closed question). **Test runs** by partners or colleagues can help to check the ease, understandability and required time of the survey.

Other factors

Developing a good survey takes **time and effort mostly at the beginning**. You need to think about which information you want to gather on the topic and from the respondents' background and based on that carefully elaborate the questions. E.g., do you need to know their occupation, gender, age or income, so that you can better understand needs or experiences of different users? We suggest asking only for **demographic data** that is relevant. Nothing more, nothing less. Demographic data can be placed at the beginning or at the end of the survey. The benefit of having the demographic data at the start is that it's less likely to be left out if not all questions are answered, but people might feel more comfortable answering questions about personal data, e.g., income, at the end.

A major challenge with surveys is to reach your respondents and motivate them to fill in the survey. This is best done as part of a wider **communication strategy**. Think about through which means (e.g., digital or paper, individual or in group, in-person or remotely) and channels (e.g., social media, newspaper, email, post, flyers), respondents can be contacted. The more diverse the group of respondents, the more useful it might be to apply different strategies. In addition, consider which information respondents need to understand the survey, its aim, relevance as well as how the results will be used.

As surveys are often answered in uncontrollable settings (e.g., on laptop at the respondent's home), responses can be more easily **influenced** by others, e.g., when respondents consult other people (Kumar, 2011) and also leave **room for reflection** as respondents can take as much time as they want, which makes them less suitable for spontaneous answers (Kumar, 2011). A common issue is that responses might **not be representative**, as often only specific groups, often the more affluent and educated, reply (Kumar, 2011), causing **bias** in the responses. Such factors need to be considered when analysing and interpreting the survey data.

Finally, in the development of the survey, the choice for method to analyse survey results need to be considered. In case of closed questions with larger respondent groups, skills in **statistical analysis** can be required, although some basic statistical analysis methods can be conducted with ease in MS Excel.

2.2 Interviews

Interviewing is a method to gather **information from diverse actors** (Kumar, 2011), such as citizens, policymakers, and entrepreneurs, by asking questions. Characteristic for an interview is that there is **personal interaction** between an interviewer and an interviewee. Although interviews are mostly known to be conducted in person, face-to-face, one-on-one, they can also be conducted through telephone or nowadays through online conference applications, e.g., Zoom, Skype, Teams (Creswell, 2014).

Interviews are particularly suitable for more complex situations or phenomena (Kumar, 2011) in which it's difficult to retrieve data through observation or more extensive explanations are needed. Interviews allow gathering **narratives on experiences, perceptions, and ideas**. What sets interviews apart from surveys is the fact that in narratives, we as interviewers can gather unexpected, unforeseen, and previously unknown information, creating added value and potential innovations for our project. Furthermore, during the interview, the interviewee sometimes processes thoughts, he or she had not considered before, which allows for internal reflection and could trigger new perspectives and adjustments of processes. Interviewees can also "provide **historical information**" (Creswell, 2014) by giving accounts and perceptions on events or phenomena in the past. E.g., as an interviewer I could ask an interviewee to tell me how participation was conducted 10 years ago in the municipality. In this sense, I could let the interviewee think about the progress that has been made in the last ten years. Nevertheless, what needs to be considered is that information from interviews is **indirect** and can be **coloured** through the viewpoints and bias of the interviewees (Creswell, 2014).

Structured or semi-structured?

With **structured interviews**, the interviewer asks the same set of pre-determined open and/or closed questions in the same sequence to each interviewee (Kumar, 2011). The advantages are that they require less interview skills and the collected data is easier to analyse and to compare (Kumar, 2011). However, due to its rigidity, there is less possibility to ask additional questions.

Semi-structured interviews also work with a predetermined list of questions or topics, but the interviewer is free to ask the questions in any order that works, to reformulate questions in their own wording, to explain questions, and to ask follow-up questions (Kumar, 2011), giving more control over the line of questioning, and the chance to steer the conversation, or select which topics to discuss in detail. They can lead to more **in-depth and rich data**, but this makes systematic analysis also more difficult and labour-intensive. As structured interviews are similar to an in-person survey, we focus on the more commonly used semi-structured interviews.

Semi-structured interviews

Within semi-structured interviews, it is important to ask **open questions**, especially at the start of the interview. Closed questions can be asked towards the end to get more concrete and precise answers. Only closed questions in an interview should be avoided, as it feels like an interrogation. The interview ends when all questions are covered or when time runs out. For the typical structure of such an interview, see 'Checklist for interviews' below.

The quality of the interview data is dependent on the interactions between parties (Kumar, 2011). Not all people are equally good at understanding the interview topic or in articulating their ideas and perceptions (Creswell, 2014). Before an interview, an interviewer needs to think about the **relevance and suitability of the potential interviewees** based on their roles, expertise and capacities. In addition, the interviewer's expertise on the topic, commitment, skills, and experience play a role in the data quality. Skills and expertise can be developed by attending and watching interviews, or interviewers can combine forces. However, it is recommended not to have more than two interviewers per interview and each interviewer should have a clear role within the interview. As the capacities of interviewers vary, conducting multiple interviews with a **variety of interviewers** can create more variation in the quality of the data (Kumar, 2011). When working with several interviewers, it can be helpful to limit the freedom in sequence and wording. This level of structure can be determined prior to the interviews. Then, the **interaction** between interviewer and interviewee(s) affects the data quality. People might not match or misunderstand each other. In addition, the **interviewer's presence may bias responses** (Creswell, 2014). If the interviewer has a "higher" social status in the perception of the interviewee, the interviewee might provide responses he or she thinks the interviewer wants to hear, e.g., if the interviewee perceives the interviewer as an expert and therefore does not want to give "wrong" answers in order not to lose face.

If the interviewee agrees to it, interviews can be recorded. **Recordings** can be made by special recording devices, smart phones, or through online conference applications. Recordings allow interviewers to focus on the interviewee, the questions and the conversation. For this reason, we recommend **note taking** only for follow-up questions during the interview. However, if recording is not possible or hindered (e.g., due to external noises), it is advisable to take notes, or preferably have a second interviewer present to take notes. If recordings are made, ensure the device has enough battery life, data storage, and is positioned in good location to ensure good quality recordings. Good quality recordings can make a big difference in the ease of transcribing the interview.

Regarding the **number of interviewees** to conduct, there are in general two factors to consider:

1. gather sufficient data on the interview topic. Normally the number of interviews is then determined by so-called **data saturation**. In other words, when new interviews do not bring in any new narratives.
2. how many interviews **feasibly** can be conducting regarding time and human resources.

2.3 Focus groups

A focus group is a specific form of interview in a **group setting** (Creswell, 2014), allowing participants to speak, discuss, and engage in conversation regarding their personal attitudes toward a specific theme, project, or idea. This method also allows exchange of ideas and building up on each others' ideas (Liamputtong 2011). In this sense, as in semi-structured interviews, focus groups offer an opportunity to expose and/or deepen insights into potentially new perspectives.

Group members are typically pre-selected to represent a particular segment of the population, or of local stakeholders. Groups usually consist of 8 to 12 members, and sessions typically last 1.5-2 hours. A moderator guides the group through a discussion based on a predefined list of questions, similar to a semi-structured interview. For the typical structure of a focus group, see 'Checklist for focus groups' below.

Moderation

The **moderator plays a crucial, and complex, role** in facilitating and guiding the discussion based on predetermined questions, ensuring the involvement of all participants, managing group dynamics, avoiding conflicts, and promoting constructive dialogue that includes and allows for the sharing of perspectives that may be quite different. If participants have diverse knowledge, skills, political influence, economic resources, or other types of resources, power disparities may affect the discussion. In such cases, those with more resources (e.g., a medium-large business compared to an individual citizen) may attempt to dominate the discussion. It is important for the moderator to observe these power disparities and try to mitigate them within the focus group or consider them when analysing or interpreting the content of the discussion.

There are tools to consider and observe **dynamics and power imbalances** within focus groups. One method is the **power cube** (Gaventa 2019), which helps enhance collaborations among several stakeholders within a focus group and reveals barriers and opportunities for action (Brisbois et al., forthcoming). There is the possibility to directly address power dynamics during the focus group discussion, or the moderator can be aware of this approach and use it later to report the discussion's content. It is important to be aware that there are several power forms, namely visible, hidden, and invisible; diverse levels of power, namely global, national, and local; and diverse power spaces, namely closed, invited, and claimed. All these components of power can influence an inclusive discussion within the focus group. Guidelines to plan a focus group explicitly focused on power dynamics are included in the PowerCube [webpage](#).

Other factors

Whether **recording** is a good idea depends on the types of participants. On the one side, recording can influence the discussion and can lead some actors (especially, but not only politicians) to not express themselves in a natural and sincere manner. On the other hand, recording is an important tool for researcher to have 'objective' information and give the opportunity to listen back to the content at a later time to ensure not to miss important elements of the conversation (Pretto 2011). Yet, as recordings of focus groups might be more difficult to transcribe, as different people talk at the same time, we recommend having at least one, but preferably multiple **note takers**. If the focus group is not recorded, **note takers** are especially needed.

3 CHECKLISTS

3.1 Checklist for surveys

Before

- Identify the indicators and the related information you want to retrieve from the survey.
- Identify the respondents you want to fill in the survey. To identify potential respondents, you can make use of [stakeholder mapping](#).
- Determine which demographic data from your respondents is relevant for the survey.
- Determine which type of questions (e.g., open, closed: Likert scale, mapping) are the most suitable to collect the required data.
- Check what questions are already available.
- Adapt existing questions and/or develop new (concise and clear) questions, while considering topic, targeted respondents, and question types.
- Optional for digital questionnaires: check providers of digital questionnaires for their suitability regarding questions, question types, targeted respondents, and data protection regulation.
- Check the comprehensibility and logical flow of the questionnaire, e.g., through testing by partners or colleagues.
- Develop a communication strategy to reach the targeted respondents.
 - Select survey method(s) to reach targeted groups, e.g., online, paper, in person, in group.
 - Identify channels to inform the targeted groups about the survey
 - Develop a cover letter to accompany the survey, which according to Kumar (2011) should include a description of:
 - The persons and/or institution conducting the survey.
 - The aim and relevance of the study.
 - Any general instructions.
 - How the data will be used and stored.
 - **!** Do not forget to add a consent form to the survey.
- Optional for in-person surveys: organise staff and identify locations for survey

During

- Conduct survey as planned
- Halfway through the duration of the survey: reflect if the received responses cover the number and type(s) of targeted respondents and adjust communication strategy accordingly
- Send reminders about the survey to targeted groups
- If in person, approach people in an open and friendly way

After

- Store the surveys and the [signed consent forms](#) according to your local rules for data storage.

- Check the survey responses for any invalid responses (e.g., when not all data is filled in, the survey is broken off midway, when important personal data is missing)
- In case of surveys in paper format, digitalise the data.
- Prepare data for analysis: in some cases, collected data needs to be cleaned, categorised or translated for it to be analysed.

3.2 Checklist for interviews

Before

- Identify the indicators and the related information you want to retrieve from the interview.
- Check what questions are already available (see the appendix of this document).
- Adapt existing questions and/or develop new (concise and clear) questions, while considering topic, targeted respondents, and question types.
- Identify a list of suitable and relevant interviewees. To identify potential interviewees, you can make use of [stakeholder mapping](#). Another way is to ask the first key interviewees to indicate who else should be interviewed regarding the topic.
- Schedule appointments with interviewees. Please consider that scheduling appointments people can require a long time. It is good practice to indicate the expected duration of the interview.
- Share the information sheet containing information about the project and how the information collected during the interview will be used and elaborated. Also, include the consent form and ensure it is sent back signed.
- Optional: Send questions prior to the interview. We recommend sending the broader interview topics, so interviewees know what they can expect and perhaps prepare some material in advance. The risk with sending the exact interview questions is that interviewees might prepare detailed (and sometimes politically correct) answers.
- Ensure your recording device functions and there is enough data storage.
- Ensure you have something to write with in case the interviewee does not agree to recording or if recording fails.

During

Introductory part

- Thank the interviewee for seeing you today and taking part in this study.
- Shortly explain the main objectives and activities of your project.
- Inform the participant, that he/she can feel free to ask questions at any stage during the interview.
- Check if the interviewee received and signed the information sheet. If not, take this opportunity to let them read the information sheet and sign the consent form.
- In case of recording, specifically ask for consent to record the interview. If consent is given, start recording.
- Explain how the data (e.g., notes, recordings, transcriptions) will be used. Ensure the interviewee that the data will be stored and shared according to the GDPR.

Questions for the introductory part

- Could you introduce the association/enterprise/institution and its main role/activity in the governance, planning and management of NBS?
 - This question allows gaining background information on the relevant roles and responsibilities of the institution related to NbS governance.
- What is your role in the association/enterprise/institution?
 - This question allows gaining background information on the interviewee regarding their current and prior relevant roles/responsibilities.

- Please describe briefly how your role is related to governance, planning, and management of NbS.
 - This question allows gaining background information on the role of the interviewee in NbS governance.

Concluding part

- Thank the interviewee for his or her time and feedback.
- Provide the interviewee with the contact details for further information, questions or comments about the interviews.

Questions for the concluding part

- Are there any topics that you think are important and have not been mentioned yet?
- Do you have any additional comments?
- Do you have any questions regarding the interview process?

After

- Go over the notes and write down all relevant information.
- Reflect after the interview, whether data saturation has been reached or whether other interviewees need to be contacted.
- In case of recording, store the recording and the [signed information sheets](#) according to your local rules for data storage.
- Optional: transcribe the recordings in text. There are different software applications available that can help with transcription, or the service of transcription agencies can be hired.

3.3 Checklist for focus groups

Before

- Identify the indicators and the related information you want to retrieve from the focus group.
- Check what questions are already available (see the appendix of this document).
- Adapt existing questions and/or develop new (concise and clear) questions, while considering topic, targeted respondents, and question types.
- Identify a list of suitable and relevant interviewees. To identify potential interviewees, you can make use of [stakeholder mapping](#).
- Nominate a moderator, make the questions available to him or her and explain the purpose and context of the focus group. Develop a focus group plan including techniques to support the discussion and capture ideas, such as voting, brainstorming, SWOT analysis. A large collection of workshop techniques can be found on [SessionLab](#).
- Prepare the necessary materials for the focus group, such as tables and chairs in sufficient numbers for participants, sticky notes, pens, sheets, and boards.
- Ensure you prepare an effective presentation of the project and the objectives of the focus group.
- Make a choice to [record](#) or [not to record](#). If you do not record, make sure to have a note taker at the table, summarizing all the interventions and discussions.
- Once participants have confirmed their attendance, send them the information sheet and consent form.

During

Introductory part

- Thank the participants for their participation.
- Shortly explain the main objectives and activities of your project and the goals of the focus group.
- Explain the rules of conduct: Let participants know that every perspective is important and holds equal value and encourage them to actively contribute to the discussion.
- Before proceeding with the focus group, check if the participants received and signed the information sheet. If not, take this opportunity to let them read the information sheet and sign the consent form.
- In case of recording, specifically ask for consent to record the focus group to all participants. If consent is given, start recording.
- In case of no recording, the notes-taker(s) will strongly contribute to summarize the discussion.
- Start proposing a first question and let the discussion proceed. The moderator needs to ensure that all participants are heard and participating into the discussion.

Concluding part

- Thank participants for their time.

- Provide participants with contact details for further information, questions or comments.

After

- Go over the notes and write down all relevant information for the co-governance assessment.
- Reflect after the focus group about power unbalances and group dynamics, which could have affected the results of the discussion.
- In case of recordings, store the recording and the signed consent forms.
- In case of no recording, ensure that the note taker adds details to the notes after the focus group, including more information that were discussed during the focus group. The notes are important to remember all the aspects of the discussion.
- Synthesize the main contents of the focus group and share it with the participants in a short report including photos of post-its, filled-in sheets, short texts, or any other produced material.

4 REFERENCE LIST

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APPENDIX 1: INDICATOR GUIDE

For some indicators which can be assessed through surveys, interviews or focus groups, we developed additional information, including example interview questions. Each factsheet contains the following information:

- The number and name of indicator.
- The indication, which governance dimensions are addressed by the indicator.
- Potential methods: survey, interview, or focus group. In bold is indicated for which method(s) example questions have been developed. If you want to apply them to another method, the questions need to be adapted.
- A short description of the indicator and information and/or tips for using any of the three methods with it.
- Guiding questions
 - Questions for surveys are provided with optional answers (e.g., yes/no, Likert scale, open answer)
 - Questions for interviews and focus groups are provided with prompt questions

Indicator 2: Complexity of rules of existing policies

Governance dimension: Policies

Methods: survey, interview, focus group

Existing policies related to NbS (e.g., regulations or incentive programmes) are clearly communicated, coordinated with one another, easy to follow and do not result in unnecessarily lengthy processes. Whether policies are unambiguous and easily understandable can be assessed by asking municipal staff about their experiences with the policies/regulations. Another possibility is to ask a group of persons, who are targeted by the policy or regulation, about their experiences or if they see any roadblocks that could prevent them from following the policy.

This indicator can be applied to a single policy or regulation, or to multiple policies or regulations. The questions below consider multiple policies or regulations. Please define in advance on which policies or regulations you want to focus.

Questions

- Can you describe the main policies/regulations (e.g., related to NbS for the city) you are aware of?
- What is the aim of the policies/regulations? Is this aim reached?
- What has been the impact of the policies/regulations?
- What have been your experiences with these policies/regulations?
- Who applies/should apply the policies/regulations?
- Is there broad information and awareness regarding the described policies/regulations?
- Are there any inconsistencies with the objectives of the policy?
- Are the policies/regulations easy to understand?
- Are the policies/regulations easy to apply?
- Are there any knowledge or resources limitations preventing the uptake?
- Are there any conflicts with other policies?
- Which challenges have you observed or experienced when applying the policies/regulations?
- Do the policies/regulations create any obstacles to achieve NBS implementation?

Indicator 8: Ensuring equitable access to NbS

Governance dimension: Politics

Methods: survey, interview, focus group, (observation)

Planning and design of the NbS project recognises differences in ability to access the space and seeks to overcome them. Advocates representing certain groups (e.g., gender, disability, migrant background) are invited to take part in early planning and design workshops, including a site visit, in order to identify physical, functional and perceived access issues.

Questions

1. Have advocates representing minority or disadvantaged groups been invited to take part in early planning and design of NbS?
 - Did certain groups (e.g., migrant, disability, gender) expressing vulnerabilities participate in the planning and design of NbS?
 - At which stages of NbS planning and design did these groups participate?
2. Have physical, functional, and perception-based needs been identified and incorporated into the design brief?
 - Have the needs of vulnerable groups been considered in the planning and design of NbS?
 - Are several kinds of needs identified (e.g., physical, functional, perception-based)?
 - Are the needs of vulnerable groups addressed in the planning and design of NbS?

Indicator 37: Strategic planning: Easy to reach intermediate actions

Governance dimension: Processes

Methods: survey, interview, focus group, (observation)

This indicator is concerned with an aspect of strategic planning. The idea of strategic planning starts with the development of a shared future vision or objectives through a collaborative process. Based on this vision or objective, intermediate outcomes and actions are formulated to reach the vision. Regular assessment of the intermediate outcomes and actions supports reflection on whether the long-term objectives or vision are being met and whether outcomes and actions need to be adjusted, but also allows for shared learning on what works and what not.

The focus of this indicator is whether easy to reach intermediate actions are set. The idea is that short-term and easy to reach intermediate actions motivate to start working together as well as to continue working together on harder to reach actions.

As intermediate actions are intrinsically linked to shared vision or objectives, we recommended to combine this indicator with the indicator on shared vision (#31) or ask about the vision to gain understanding of the context.

A focus group could be organized to not only gain insight from different people on the strategic planning within their city, but it also allows people to discuss and reflect together the set vision, the long-term objectives, the intermediate and short-term actions.

Interview questions

1. Is there a vision developed and formalized for the preservation and development of nature-based solutions in the city in the next 20-30 years?
 - Can you describe this vision in short?
2. Have short-term and intermediate outcomes/actions to reach the long-term goals from the vision be formulated and implemented?
 - Can you give an example of an intermediate and/or short-term action and how it contributes to the long-term vision?
3. How has the implementation of short-term and/or easy to reach intermediate outcomes/actions supported the collaborative process?
4. How did these short-term and/or easy to reach intermediate outcomes/actions provided opportunities for shared learning?

Indicator 56: Governance ICT maturity - knowledge representation

Governance dimension: Institutional technologies

Methods: survey, interview

This indicator refers to the maturity of public-interest data representations (visuals, charts, published data, infographics) as measured against an industry standard. In other words, it refers to how advanced the visualization of data analysis is compared to available standards. This could include data analysts or NbS communicators in terms of how they present information (e.g., impact results). This indicator could also refer to the data visualization tools used to communicate complex data relationships and data-driven insights in a way that is easy to understand (IBM, 2023). They serve as visual aids to make informed decisions, communicate results, and evaluate data in a more accessible way, etc.

Questions

1. Is the data presented in a clear, accessible, actionable, user-friendly, unbiased, and comprehensive manner?
 - In what platform or visual form is the data presented?
 - Are there any barriers to the way the data is presented? Barriers may include:
 - Clear communication with stakeholders
 - Setting expectations and identifying the essential areas
 - Bridging the design-development gap
 - Optimization of product display for increase user engagement
 - Accessible and inclusive design
 - Adaptable interface design to different devices
 - Are the barriers specific to certain social groups?
 - If so, which ones?
2. What are the established benchmarks (standards) for knowledge representation in this Nbs?
 - Do the visualizations, tables, and published data align with established following standards? For example:
 - The representation does not cause false expectations. The confidence in the story told is communicated alongside the story itself.
 - The story told matches the data.
 - The implied message is congruent with the actual message
 - The impact the visual will have on a variety of audiences is accounted for
 - The visual does not hide or distort information.
 - Data is depicted accurately
 - The communicator is accountable personally for their work.
 - Context and reference are provided when necessary to avoid oversimplification
 - Potential fallacies of the underlying data and interpretation, and the risk they pose is communicated adequately
3. How is the data representation involved in decision-making processes?

- To what extent does it act like an important factor in deciding which direction to take?
- In which project phases is data pulled into discussions, and where is it missing?
- What could be improved to better to communicate the data?

References

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Indicator 89: Experiences of municipal staff in interdepartmental collaboration

Governance dimension: Actors, politics, processes

Methods: survey, interview

The aim of this indicator is to reflect on the experiences of working together with other departments and on how this integrated working supports or hinders the planning and implementation of NbS. In preparation for the interview, have a look at the organizational structure for planning, implementing and managing the NbS project (e.g., staff organigram or own knowledge), if you are not familiar with it yet. Knowing the organizational structure can help to identify gaps in interdepartmental collaborations.

Questions

1. With which departments/other policy domains do you collaborate?
 - What is the reason for this/these collaboration(s)?
2. What are your experiences in these collaborations?
 - What are the benefits of this/these collaboration(s)?
 - How does this/these collaboration(s) support the planning, design and management of NbS?
 - How does this collaboration affect your work?
 - What do you think makes this/these collaboration(s) successful?
 - How can this/these collaboration(s) be better supported?
 - Do the benefits of collaborating weigh up to the disbenefits?
3. With which department(s)/policy domain(s) would you like to collaborate more?
 - For which reason(s) would you like to collaborate more?
 - How could this/these collaboration(s) support the planning, design and management of NbS?
 - What are the reasons why collaboration has been limited so far?
4. With which department should you collaborate more to improve the planning, design and management of NbS?
5. You have not mentioned department X so far. Do you see reasons or opportunities to collaborate with this department?
6. Do you think that the organizational structure enables or hinders the collaboration between different departments?
 - Could you explain why?
 - How should the organization structure be improved to better support collaboration between departments?
7. Do you feel supported by your department leaders to collaborate with other departments?
 - Can you explain why?
 - How could department leaders support collaboration with other departments more or better?
8. Do you think there is political support for collaboration between departments?
 - Could you explain why?
 - How should the organization structure be improved to better support collaboration between departments?